

SELF-CONTROL RULES OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER

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Abstract. *This study analyzes the rules of self-management, awareness of one's own emotions, control of internal states, reflection and maintaining emotional stability of a psychologist-trainer in the process of conducting psychological trainings. The self-control competence of a psychologist-trainer is considered one of the leading factors determining the quality of psychological trainings. The study also considers the management of psychological problem situations that arise during psychological training, maintaining personal boundaries, preventing emotional exhaustion and metareflection approaches.*

Keywords: *psychological training, trainer competence, self-control, emotional stability, metareflection, transference, countertransference.*

ПРАВИЛА САМОКОНТРОЛЯ ПСИХОЛОГА-ТРЕНЕРА

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании анализируются правила самоменеджмента, понимания собственных эмоций, контроля внутренних состояний, рефлексии и поддержания эмоциональной устойчивости психолога-тренера в процессе проведения психологического тренинга. Компетентность психолога-тренера в области саморегуляции считается одним из ведущих факторов, определяющих качество психологической подготовки. В исследовании также обсуждаются вопросы управления психологическими проблемными ситуациями, возникающими в ходе психологического тренинга, поддержания личных границ, предотвращения эмоционального истощения и подходы метарефлексии.*

Ключевые слова: *психологическая подготовка, компетентность тренера, самоконтроль, эмоциональная устойчивость, метарефлексия, перенос, контрперенос.*

PSIXOLOG-TRENERNING O'Z-O'ZINI NAZORAT QILISH QOIDALARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda psixologik treninglarni olib borish jarayonlarida psixolog-trener shaxsining o'zini idora qilish, o'z hissiyotlarini anglash, ichki holatlarini nazorat qilish, refleksiya va emotsional barqarorlikni saqlash qoidalari tahlil etiladi. Psixolog-Trenerning o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish kompetensiyasi psixologik treninglar sifatini belgilovchi yetakchi omillardan biri sifatida qaraladi. Tadqiqotda shuningdek, psixologik trening jarayonida yuzaga keladigan psixologik muammoli holatlarini boshqarish haqida, shaxsiy chegaralarni saqlash, emotsional charchashning oldini olish va metarefleksiya yondashuvlari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: psixologik trening, trener kompetensiyasi, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish, emotsional barqarorlik, metarefleksiya, transferens, kontrtransferens.

KIRISH

Psychological training is a complex psychological process aimed at changing individual and group mental states, emotional experiences, behavioral patterns and social relationships. Successful organization of this process requires the trainer not only theoretical knowledge and methodological skills, but also a high level of self-awareness, the ability to manage their emotions and a responsible attitude towards their own internal state. Because during the training, the trainer acts not only as a manager of the learning process, but also as a psychological “methodology” of the participants. Therefore, the rules of self-control of the trainer when conducting psychological training are of particular scientific and practical importance, and this article is devoted to this issue.

The first important principle of self-control for a psychologist-trainer is to ensure emotional awareness and stability. During psychological training, various psychological reactions of participants - fear, aggression, indifference or excessive openness - can provoke various emotional responses in the trainer. If the trainer does not understand these situations in time and cannot consciously control them, then the communicative balance in the training will be disrupted.

Therefore, the trainer should always analyze his own state through internal questions such as “what am I feeling now?”, “how do these feelings of mine affect the condition of the participant?” This reflective approach helps to manage emotional reactions and separate personal feelings from the training process. The second important rule is the principle of clearly defining and adhering to psychological boundaries. During the training process, close emotional bonds can form with participants. In such cases, the trainer must be able to balance sincerity and professional neutrality. The trainer should never interfere excessively in the personal problems of the participants, directly influence their life choices or personal decisions. This, in turn, means ethical responsibility and adherence to professional boundaries.

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Another important aspect is the ability to manage transference and countertransference situations. Transference is the emotional attitude of the participant towards the trainer based on his previous life experience, while countertransference is the trainer's response emotions towards him.

For example, a participant's low self-esteem may arouse in the trainer a desire to "protect" him. However, this situation can hinder independent development. Therefore, the trainer must be aware of such internal impulses and manage them from a methodologically neutral and professional position. In addition, psychophysiological approaches such as working with the body and breathing are also important in self-control. The trainer should monitor his body position, breathing rhythm and level of tension, especially during long sessions. Short autogenic relaxation exercises or meditation pauses after stressful training can help the trainer to restore his condition.

Also, regular use of such self-restorative techniques before and after training can prevent emotional stress. Another necessary step in self-control for the trainer is the formation of metareflexive thinking, that is, by constantly analyzing not only the question "how did the training go?", but also questions such as "what role did I play?", "what result did my approach give?", "what internal state was I in?", this creates the opportunity to deeply understand and improve his professional position. Such metareflexion elevates the trainer to the level of conscious professionalism, not just as a provider of knowledge, but as a self-improver. In modern psychological practice, the trainer's self-control is considered not only a product of individual reflection, but also a central factor in the formation of the trainer's identity. How the trainer imagines himself, what task he considers himself to have taken on, all his decisions and actions are formed on the basis of this internal identification. Therefore, during the training process, the trainer must clearly define his role, be able to act appropriately between the roles of "trainer - group leader - supporter - observer". If the trainer allows confusion between these roles, the participants begin to feel psychologically unoriented and in an uncertain environment. This situation weakens the group dynamics and reduces the effectiveness of the training. In addition, the use of the dynamic self-observation model in self-control is relevant. According to this model, the trainer notices each of his psychological reactions in real time through his stream of thoughts, body reactions, internal dialogue and intuition. Especially in the case of "projected issues", that is, when the participant's internal conflicts are imposed on the trainer "from above", the trainer must be able to protect his emotional space, maintain professional neutrality by understanding it.

Otherwise, the training will turn into individual therapy and the group's potential will be lost.

Conclusion

In the successful conduct of psychological training, the trainer's self-control is not just a culture of behavior or restraint of emotions, but a set of complex psychological competencies.

These competencies include internal sensitivity, emotional awareness, reflexive analysis, maintaining professional boundaries, stress tolerance, ethical responsibility and psychological commitment. If the trainer cannot control himself in training, the dynamics of the entire group will be disrupted. Therefore, self-control is more important than knowledge of any methodology and should be recognized as the basis of coaching activities.

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